

30 **Abstracts:**

31 Biological soil crusts (BSCs) are essential components of drylands, yet the effects of their
32 development on soil multifunctionality (SMF) and the drivers behind these effects remain unclear.
33 We sampled 11 sites in Northwest China's deserts, representing different successional stages of BSC
34 development (i.e. cyanobacterial, lichen and moss crusts) as well as bare sand areas. We assessed
35 the SMF of the crust layer and underlying soil at various depths (0-2, 2-5, 5-10, 10-20 cm) and also
36 explored the influence of climatic factors (mean annual temperature, aridity, and solar radiation),
37 crust characteristics (compressive strength, roughness, and thickness), and soil properties (pH,
38 electrical conductivity, soil water content) on SMF across these layers. The presence of BSCs
39 significantly enhanced soil nutritional status [soil organic carbon (SOC), total nitrogen (TN), total
40 phosphorus (TP), ammonia ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$), nitrate ($\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$), and available phosphorus (AP)] throughout
41 the 0-20 cm soil depth and increased SMF in the top 0-10 cm. These positive effects intensified with
42 as BSCs progressed from cyanobacterial to lichen to moss stages, but decreased with soil depth. In
43 the crust layer, SMF across all BSC types was positively influenced by our climatic factors.
44 However, as BSCs developed, the negative influence of climatic factors (mainly solar radiation) and
45 soil properties (mainly pH) on SMF decreased, while the positive influence of crust characteristics
46 (mainly thickness) increased. The influence of climate, crust, and soil factors on SMF also decreased
47 with increasing soil depth and varied by BSC type. Further, our findings demonstrate that the BSC
48 development can buffer the negative effects of increased soil pH and solar radiation on SMF while
49 enhancing the positive effects of crust properties, particularly thickness. This highlights the
50 importance of preserving and promoting BSC development to enhance surface soil
51 multifunctionality and mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on dryland ecosystem
52 multifunctionality.

53 **Keywords:** drylands, biological soil crusts, soil depths, driving factors, successional stage

54

55 **1. Introduction**

56 Drylands, covering approximately 45% of the Earth's land surface, are characterized by sparse
57 vegetation and high sensitivity to environmental changes (Pravalié, 2016). Biological Soil Crusts
58 (BSCs), composed of cryptogamic organisms (e.g., bacteria, cyanobacteria, fungi, lichens, and
59 mosses) integrated with soil particles, are widespread and play a critical role in these regions
60 (Witzgall et al., 2024). Recent research estimates that BSCs cover around 12% of the Earth's
61 terrestrial surface and around 30% of global dryland soils (Rodríguez-Caballero et al., 2018). These
62 crusts significantly enhance the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the topsoil,
63 facilitating essential processes such as nutrient cycling and energy exchange (Bowker et al., 2018).
64 Additionally, BSCs contribute to diverse ecological functions such as wind erosion control, sand
65 stabilization, water and heat regulation, carbon and nitrogen sequestration, soil enzyme activity
66 enhancement, and biodiversity promotion (Gao et al., 2020; Hu et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021; Zhou et
67 al., 2020). They are also crucial in soil and vegetation restoration (Lan et al., 2014), demonstrating
68 remarkable resilience to extreme drought and harsh environments, allowing them to pioneer soil
69 formation and primary succession (Maier et al., 2018). Consequently, BSCs are fundamental in
70 shaping dryland ecosystems and provide valuable models for studying ecological processes at the
71 community, landscape, and ecosystem levels (Bowker et al., 2014).

72 Soil is a vital component of Earth's living system, providing essential foundation material and
73 ecological services necessary for human survival and sustainable development (Soliveres et al.,
74 2014). Soil multifunctionality (SMF) originates from the concept of ecosystem multifunctionality
75 (EMF), which refers to the simultaneous provision of multiple soil functions and processes (e.g.,
76 carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus cycling, hydrological regulation, and biodiversity maintenance,
77 etc.) that support the provision of ecosystem services, allows the assessment of combined impacts
78 of multiple environmental factors (Bünemann et al., 2018; Duran et al., 2018). Research into SMF,
79 is therefore critical for deepening our understanding of the soil's overall service capacity (Creamer
80 et al., 2022; Manning et al., 2018) and for improving our capacity to preserve and enhance
81 ecosystem functions and services (Marquardt et al., 2019).

82 Recent studies have demonstrated that BSCs influence many aspects of dryland ecosystems
83 (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2016; Eldridge et al., 2020). As BSCs develop, they alter various
84 ecosystem features, including soil surface microenvironments, water-nutrient content, and particle

85 composition (Liu et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2021; Chamizo et al., 2012; Rodriguez-Caballero et al.,
86 2018), as well as plant growth and population dynamics (Song et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019). For
87 instance, surface soil nutrients, salt content, and soil enzyme activities significantly and consistently
88 increased with the succession from cyanobacterial to lichen and moss crusts (Zhang et al., 2015).
89 Some recent studies suggest that all these changes should influence SMF (Xu et al., 2021a). For
90 instance, BSCs diversity has been recognized as the main driver of SMF and to be closely linked to
91 numerous soil processes and functions (Bowker et al., 2014; Ortiz et al., 2023), and Delgado-
92 Baquerizo et al., (2016) demonstrated that biocrust-forming mosses mitigate the negative effects of
93 increasing aridity on ecosystem multifunctionality. However, the degree of influence and driving
94 factors of different crusts on SMF remain largely unknown, let alone the soil depth to which these
95 effects extend, as few studies have examined the effect of BSCs on SMF at different soil depths.
96 Further, while previous studies investigating the environmental drivers of SMF have primarily
97 focused on soil or climatic attributes such as pH or mean annual precipitation and temperature, the
98 BSCs possess unique physical properties that can significantly alter soil properties such as water
99 infiltration, aggregate stability, or moisture retention (Kidron et al., 2020). The extent to which these
100 physical properties of BSCs affect SMF, and how their influence compares to climatic and soil
101 factors remains unexplored. Moreover, most current research on the influence of BSCs on SMF has
102 been conducted at the site scale, without considering the broader functional heterogeneity of soils
103 at larger scales.

104 We conducted a large-scale survey across 11 independent sites located at the drylands of
105 Northwest China, encompassing over 2200 km, to examine how BSCs and other environmental
106 factors jointly influence SMF at various soil depths and stages of BSC succession (cyanobacterial,
107 lichen and moss; Fig. 1). Given that BSCs development can promote a gradual increase in soil
108 nutritional status (Zhang et al., 2015), we hypothesized that SMF would increase with BSCs
109 succession and decrease with increasing soil depths as the influence of the BSCs diminishes. Further,
110 based on the fact that crust properties may influence soil physical structure and that different crust
111 types may vary in their response to climate and influence on soil properties (Felde et al., 2014;
112 Zhang et al., 2015), we also hypothesized that the drivers of SMF would vary across crust types.
113 Finally, considering that the soil in the crust layer is in close contact with climatic conditions (Huang
114 et al., 2023), we further hypothesized that climatic factors would play a stronger role in the crust

115 layer, with soil-related factors becoming more dominant at greater depths.

116 **2. Materials and Methods**

117 *2.1 Overview of study site and method of soil sampling*

118 The Northwest Drylands of China constitute an extensive arid region covering approximately
119 one-quarter of the country's land area (Fig. 1). This area is characterized by a fragile ecological
120 environment, minimal rainfall and prevalent drought conditions. Vegetation is sparse, dominated by
121 small salt- and drought-tolerant shrubs and herbaceous plants that provide limited ground coverage.

122 In July-August 2021, 11 sampling sites were selected based on preliminary fieldwork (Figure.
123 1) across four major Chinese deserts, Gurbantunggut (G1-3), Kubuqi (G4), Mu Us (G5-8), and
124 Tengger (G9-11). Sites were chosen to (1) ensure a broad distribution across different deserts while
125 avoiding the central Gobi area due to the absence of well-developed BSCs; (2) to include bare sand
126 and three well-developed BSCs [Cyanobacterial crust (lichen and moss coverages < 20 %), Lichen
127 crust (lichen coverage >20 % but moss coverage < 20 %), Moss crust (moss coverage >75 %)] areas
128 at all sites (Lan et al., 2013), and subsequent high-throughput sequencing confirmed that
129 cyanobacterial crusts were predominantly *Microcoleus*, minimizing functional differences between
130 species; and (3) to minimize anthropogenic disturbance maintaining a minimum of 3 km distance
131 from any road. At each site, we established five 10 m × 10 m replicate plots (Regarded as five
132 biological repetitions). Based on the distribution patterns of bare sand and biological soil crusts
133 (BSCs), four 1 m × 1 m subplots (for bare sand, cyanobacterial crust, lichen crust, and moss crust,
134 respectively) were established within each main plot. A five-point sampling method (samples
135 collected from four corners and the center of each subplot, then homogenized into a composite
136 sample) was implemented for sampling to capture fine-scale spatial heterogeneity of soil nutrients
137 (Tao et al., 2017). Soil samples were collected from the crust layer and sub-crust depths (i.e. 0-2, 2-
138 5, 5-10, 10-20 cm), fine-scale sampling intervals in surface layers allow precise capture of BSCs'
139 regulatory effects on surface microenvironments (0-2, 2-5 cm), while coarser intervals in deeper
140 layers are used because deeper soil physicochemical properties change more slowly over time; thus,
141 larger intervals (5-10, 10-20 cm) sufficiently characterize long-term trends while minimizing
142 sampling and analytical costs. The crust layer, a colloidal complex of cryptogams and associated
143 soil microorganisms and particles, was treated as a cyanobacterial/lichen-soil complex due to

144 inseparability. However, for moss crusts, this layer was carefully stripped of moss tissue, and after
145 thorough removal of moss residue using a 2 mm sieve, the collected soil was considered moss crust
146 layer soil. This design yielded 55 samples per soil depth (11 sampling sites \times 5 replicate plots) for
147 both bare sand and the three BSC types.

148 We determined the physical properties of the BSCs in the field. Crust compressive strength (Cs)
149 was assessed with a hand-held gauge ring (contact surface diameter: 4.40 mm; mass: 0.97497 kg;
150 readout rate factor: 2.5664 N / 0.01 mm). Crust total pressure and compressive strength were
151 calculated as: total pressure = gauge ring readout \times rate factor + weight of gauge ring (N);
152 compressive strength = total pressure / contact surface area. Crust thickness (Tn) was determined
153 using vernier calipers. Crust roughness (Rs) was measured by the chain method (1m length, 3 mm
154 width metal chain; measurements repeated five times for each crust), and calculated as $R_s = (1 -$
155 $L_2/L_1) \times 100\%$, where L1 is the chain length and L2 is the horizontal length of the chain after laying
156 on the ground.

157 *2.2 Soil physicochemical properties*

158 We selected six key indicators of ecosystem functionality, namely soil organic carbon (SOC),
159 total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP), ammonia ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$), nitrate ($\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$), and available
160 phosphorus (AP). These six indicators can reflect the nutrient cycling and retention functions of
161 carbon(C), nitrogen(N), and phosphorus(P) (Valencia et al., 2015b; Yan et al., 2020).

162 Before analyses, soil samples were sieved to 2 mm, ground with a ball mill, and passed through
163 a 0.15 mm sieve. SOC was determined by hydrochloric acid-dry combustion method (Multi N/C
164 3100 TOC analyzer, Analytik Jena, Germany); TN by the Kjeldahl method; and TP by molybdenum-
165 antimony-scandium colorimetry (AA3 Auto Analyzer 3, Seal, Jena, Germany, Seal, Jena, Germany).
166 Soil inorganic N (i.e. $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$) and AP was extracted shaking for 1h with KCl (10:1
167 solution-to-soil ratio), and AP with NaHCO_3 (1:1), respectively, and analyzed via by continuous
168 flow (AA3 Auto Analyzer 3, Seal, Jena, Germany). Soil pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were
169 measured according to standards (HJ 962-2018) developed by the Ministry of Ecology and
170 Environment of the People's Republic of China, using water-soil ratios of 2.5:1 for pH and 5:1 for
171 EC. Soil water content (SWC) was determined by oven drying at 105°C for 24 hours.

172 *2.3 SMF quantification*

173 Currently, there are multiple common methods for quantifying soil multifunctionality (SMF)

174 in ecosystems, such as the averaging method (Hooper & Vitousek, 2005), functional species
175 replacement method (Hector & Bagchi, 2007), single-threshold method (Gamfeldt et al., 2008), and
176 multiple-thresholds method (Byrnes et al., 2014). Each method has its own advantages and
177 limitations. Among these, the averaging method quantifies ecosystem multifunctionality by
178 calculating the mean standardized scores (Z-scores) of different ecosystem functions. This method
179 provides a straightforward way to evaluate the capacity of ecosystems to sustain multiple functions
180 simultaneously and is particularly suitable for cross-regional comparative studies. Therefore, among
181 existing SMF quantification methods, we adopted the averaging method, in which SMF is calculated
182 as:

$$183 \quad \text{SMF} = \frac{1}{F} \sum_{i=1}^F g(\text{ri}(f_i))$$

184 f_i is each function's measured value, ri is a mathematical function that transforms f_i values to
185 positive, g normalizes the data, and F is the number of functions.

186 *2.4 Climate data acquisition*

187 Based on established practices from previous studies (Zhang et al., 2022), we selected Mean
188 annual temperature (MAT), aridity index (AI), and solar radiation (Srad) as representative indicators
189 of arid-region climatic characteristics (high temperature, aridity, and intense radiation). Climate data
190 were sourced from multiple databases. MAT data were obtained from the MODIS MOD11A Global
191 Temperature Grid (<https://doi.org/10.5067/MODIS/MOD11A1.006>), a MOD11A1 V6 product that
192 provides daily surface temperature (LSTV) and emissivity values in a 1 km grid (Rodell et al., 2004).
193 AI data were extracted from the CGIAR raster (Consortium for Spatial Information; 1x1 km
194 resolution; (Hu et al., 2021). Srad data was obtained from the Terra Climate dataset (University of
195 Idaho; <https://doi:10.1038/sdata.2017.191>; Yan et al., 2020), which includes the global land surface
196 monthly average climate and climate water balance datasets, as well as climate data such as annual
197 rainfall data (MAP), potential evapotranspiration (PET), and actual evapotranspiration (AET).

198 *2.5 Statistical analysis*

199 All statistical analyses and mapping were conducted in R 4.2.2. To explore how soil nutrient
200 and SMF vary under bare sand and different crust covers, we fitted linear mixed-effects models
201 using the "lme 4" package (Bates et al.(2015), with "sampling point" included as a random effect.
202 Multiple comparisons among BSCs and soil depths were explored using the "lsmeans" package.

203 Box plots illustrating soil nutrient and SMF variability were generated with "ggplot2". Ordinary
204 Least Squares (OLS) regressions were conducted using "ggplot2" to explore relationships between
205 environmental factors (e.g. climate, crust and soil factors) and SMF, with Z-score standardization
206 of environmental data. Random forest analyses ("ggRandomForests" package) were used to identify
207 the most important predictors influencing SMF by assessing variable importance across multiple
208 decision trees, whereas variance decomposition ("varpart" function of the "vegan") was used to
209 quantify the proportion of variability in SMF explained by each predictor, providing insight into
210 their relative contributions within the model. Finally, partial least squares path models were
211 constructed using the "plsrm" package to explore the direct and indirect drivers of SMF across crust
212 types.

213 **3. Results**

214 *3.1 Soil properties*

215 Soil nutrient content, particularly SOC and TN significantly and progressively increased as
216 BSCs advanced through successional stages from bare areas to cyanobacterial, lichen, and moss
217 crusts (Fig. 2). However, at certain depths (i.e. 0-2 cm and 10-20 cm), soil $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content was
218 higher in bare areas than in crust-covered soils. We also found a notable decline in total soil nutrient
219 content (SOC, TN, TP), along with diminishing differences among cover types, with increasing soil
220 depths.

221 *3.2 Soil multifunctionality*

222 Similar to soil properties, SMF values increased consistently across BSC successional stages
223 (cyanobacterial to lichen to moss; Fig. 3), particularly in the crust layers. The highest SMF was
224 observed in the moss crust layer (ranging from 1.68 to 2.38), followed by the lichen (0.87 to 1.49),
225 and the cyanobacterial crust (0.53. to 1.21) layers, with bare sand exhibiting the lowest SMF (-0.83
226 to 0.08). Significant differences in SMF were found among crust types at both the crust layer and
227 the 0-2 cm soil depth, but these differences diminished with increasing soil depth. For instance, at
228 the 2-5 cm depth, SMF values for the lichen crust layer were not significantly different from those
229 of the moss crust layer, though both were still substantially higher than the SMF values for the
230 cyanobacterial crust layer and bare sand. At greater depths (10-20 cm), SMF in bare sand
231 significantly differs from that in crust type.

232 *3.3 Environmental drivers of SMF*

233 Climatic variables affected SMF differently across crust layers and soil depths (Fig. 4). For
234 instance, the SMF of the crust layer of all three crust types was not significantly correlated with
235 mean annual temperature (MAT), but SMF at deeper soil depths showed a negative correlation with
236 MAT. Additionally, aridity was negatively correlated with SMF in lichen crust layers but positively
237 at deeper depths. Similarly, solar radiation (Srad) positively correlated with SMF in the crust layers
238 across all BSCs but had a negative correlation with SMF at deeper depths.

239 Under cyanobacterial and lichen crusts, SMF was positively correlated with compressive
240 strength (Cs) at both the crust layer and the 2-5 cm soil depth, while SMF under the moss crust
241 displayed a negative correlation with Cs (Fig. S1). No significant correlations were observed
242 between SMF at the crust layer and crust roughness (Rs) for any of the three crust types. However,

243 Rs correlated positively with SMF at deeper soil depths. SMF under moss crusts showed strong
244 positive correlations with crust thickness (Tn) at all depths. There was also a significant and positive
245 correlation between SMF and Tn in cyanobacterial crusts at the 0-20 cm soil depths, while a
246 significant and positive correlation between SMF and Tn in lichen crusts was only observed at the
247 0-2 cm and 5-10 cm soil depths.

248 The SMF of cyanobacteria and lichen crust layer was negatively correlated with pH, but
249 positively correlated at deeper depths (Fig. S2). Across various depths, SMF under all crust types
250 showed varying degrees of positive correlations with soil electrical conductivity (EC). However,
251 SMF under lichen crusts displayed a weaker correlation with EC and a positive correlation with soil
252 water content (SWC) only at the 0-2 and 10-20 cm soil depths. The correlation between SWC and
253 SMF varied by crust type. For instance, SMF under cyanobacterial crusts showed a significant
254 positive correlation with SWC at 2-5 cm, while under lichen crusts, SMF was positively correlated
255 with SWC at the crust layer and at 2-5 cm. In contrast, SMF under moss crusts correlated with SWC
256 at the 0-10 cm soil depth.

257 *3.4 Relative importance of climate, crust and soil properties driving SMF*

258 Random forest analyses (Fig. 5) and variance partitioning (Fig. S3) showed that climate, crust,
259 and soil factors together explained between 86.49% and 51.31% of the variation in SMF, with the
260 explanatory power gradually decreasing with increasing of soil depth. Climate was a dominant
261 driver of SMF across soil depths for all crust types. For the cyanobacterial crust, climate factors
262 independently explained 25.81% to 43.80% of the variation in SMF across different soil depths,
263 with climate remaining the strongest predictor at all depths. For lichen crusts, climate independently
264 explained 1.72% to 21.50% of SMF variation across different soil depths, with compressive strength
265 (Cs) as key predictors for the crust layer and 2-5 cm and 10-20 cm depths; MAT for the 0-2 cm
266 depth; and Tn for the 5-10 cm depth. For moss crusts, climate factors independently accounted for
267 1.19%-22.83% of the SMF variation across depths, with soil properties and climate factors—
268 specifically electrical conductivity (EC) in the crust layer, aridity at 0-2 cm, pH at 2-5 cm and 10-
269 20 cm, and Srad at 5-10 cm—emerging as the strongest predictors.

270 *3.5 Direct and indirect effects of SMF drivers*

271 The structural equation models indicate that the variance explained by our models ranged from
272 28 to 73% (Fig. 6). For the crust layer, as crusts progressed from cyanobacterial to lichen to moss,

273 the overall influence of climatic factors on SMF decreased (with no significant differences between
274 lichen and moss crusts), while the influence of soil and crust factors on SMF gradually decreased
275 and increased, respectively. For cyanobacterial crusts, SMF was primarily negatively affected by
276 the analyzed soil factors (path coefficient: -0.77), and positively by our climate factors (0.74). In
277 contrast, SMF under lichen and moss crusts was mainly positively influenced by the considered
278 climatic factors (0.64 and 0.63, respectively), whereas crust factors had a negative impact on lichen
279 crust SMF (-0.34) and a non-significant effect on moss crust SMF (0.17). At the 0-2 cm depth, SMF
280 across all crust types was primarily and negatively affected by climate, with path coefficients of -
281 0.89, -0.64, and -0.46 for cyanobacterial, lichen, and moss crusts, respectively (i.e. with effects
282 progressively decreasing with crust succession). With the deepening of soil depth (2-20 cm), the
283 influence coefficients of each factor (climate, crust, soil) on SMF of the three kinds of crust
284 decreased to varying degrees. The influence of the three factors on SMF of lichen crust became
285 insignificant, but the negative influence of climate factors on SMF of cyanobacteria crust was still
286 significant (-0.60, -0.62, -0.34), and the positive effect of crust on SMF of 2 ~ 5 cm moss crust was
287 still significant (0.38).

288 **4. Discussion**

289 *4.1 BSC succession drives surface soil nutrient and SMF enhancement*

290 As hypothesized, soil multifunctionality (SMF) increased significantly with the succession of
291 biological soil crusts (BSCs) from cyanobacterial to lichen, and ultimately to moss. This
292 enhancement was particularly evident in the crust layer and the 0-2 cm soil depth. Our findings align
293 with previous research in the Gurbantunggut Desert, which also reported improved ecosystem
294 multifunctionality across these three BSC types (Xu et al., 2021b). In nutrient-poor desert soils, this
295 improvement in SMF can largely be attributed to increased availability of key elements, namely
296 carbon (C), nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) (Jones et al., 2023). BSCs are key contributors to
297 nutrient cycling and serve as essential indicators of soil health, contributing significantly to soil
298 organic C and total N through photosynthesis and N fixation (Belnap et al., 2001; Evans & Johansen,
299 1999; Tucker et al., 2020). As BSCs mature, their capacity to photosynthesize (Zhao et al., 2016b)
300 and fixate N (Pietrasiak et al., 2013) increases, primarily enrich surface soil depth (0-5 cm) with
301 organic SOC and TN (Xu et al., 2021b). In addition, the root-like structures of fungi, lichens, and
302 mosses penetrate rock crevices and release organic acids, facilitating mineral decomposition and

303 weathering (Banfield et al., 1999). This process is critical for increasing the availability of inorganic
304 ions, especially phosphorus, which primarily enters desert soils through rock weathering (Deiss et
305 al., 2018).

306 Among the three BSC types, we found moss crusts to be the most effective in promoting SMF,
307 which can be explained by several factors. (1) Structural stabilization and biodiversity maintenance:
308 moss crusts form patches that stabilize the soil surface and create “fertility islands”, helping to
309 maintain species diversity through their well-developed pseudo-root systems (Maestre et al., 2012);
310 (2) Hydrological regulation and nutrient activation: their high water retention capacity enhances the
311 capture of atmospheric condensation, vapor, and fog, increasing microbial activity by enhancing
312 surface water availability (Liu et al., 2006). And this hydrological regulation capability activates
313 soil enzyme activity, accelerating organic matter mineralization and nutrient release. Additionally,
314 moss-secreted organic acids (e.g., oxalic and citric acids) dissolve sparingly soluble minerals (e.g.,
315 apatite), liberating plant-available phosphates (Banfield et al., 1999); (3) Microbial-driven carbon
316 sequestration: Moss coverage increases microbial biomass carbon (MBC) by 2–3 times, enhancing
317 carbon sequestration efficiency through litter input and microclimate regulation (Zhao et al., 2016a);
318 (4) Stress resistance and ecological resilience: moss crusts exhibit superior erosion resistance
319 compared to other crust types (Silva et al., 2019) and contain totipotent cells, enabling rapid
320 recovery and prolonged viability under favorable conditions (Zhao et al., 2016a). Interestingly, as
321 soil depth increased, the differences in SMF between crust types diminished, with no significant
322 differences observed at the 10–20 cm soil depth. This supports our hypothesis that BSCs strongly
323 influence surface soil fertility but have limited impact at greater depths, primarily benefiting
324 shallow-rooted herbaceous plants and creating a mosaic landscape of BSCs and herbaceous
325 vegetation (Li et al., 2005).

326 These findings not only demonstrate that the progression from cyanobacterial to lichen to moss
327 crusts enhances SMF by improving nutrient cycling and stabilizing soil surfaces, but also emphasize
328 the crucial role of BSCs in promoting vascular plant distribution and promoting herbaceous plant
329 growth in dryland regions through enhanced nutrient supply.

330 *4.2 Opposing effects of climatic factors on SMF in the crust layer and the subsoil*

331 Our results indicate that the drivers of SMF shift significantly as BSCs develop. Nevertheless,
332 and supporting our second hypothesis, climate remained as the most important driver of SMF, likely

333 because the soil in the crust layer, being directly exposed, is highly responsive to environmental
334 changes (Liu et al., 2024). Climate change factors such as rising temperatures, reduced precipitation,
335 and increased solar radiation, can alter plant community structure and soil microbial diversity and
336 abundance, thereby threatening soil ecosystem functioning (Maestre et al., 2012; Valencia et al.,
337 2015a). Our analysis of the bare soil confirmed a significant negative correlation between mean
338 annual temperature, solar radiation, and SMF, suggesting that global climate change will pose
339 substantial risks to soil functionality in drylands in coming years under climate change scenarios
340 (Hu et al., 2021).

341 Interestingly, we found that climatic factors have opposite effects in the crust layer (positive)
342 and the underlying soil depths (negative). Specifically, mean annual temperature showed no
343 significant relationship with SMF in the crust, while solar radiation was positively correlated with
344 SMF in the crust but negatively in the subsoil. The structural equation models further revealed an
345 overall positive climate effect on the crust layer but a negative effect on the subsoil. These results
346 highlight the complexity of understanding the effects of climate change on different soil
347 compartments, as well as the importance of considering various soil depths when attempting to
348 predict the fate of soil multifunctionality in the coming decades. We propose two main reasons
349 behind these patterns. The first one has to do with the biological protective strategies of the BSCs.
350 Solar radiation may enhance pigment production in BSCs, providing photoprotection in high-
351 radiation environments (Palmqvist & Sundberg, 2000; Paoli et al., 2010). Cyanobacteria in desert
352 environments are known to resist UV damage through antioxidant systems and efficient repair
353 mechanisms (Wang et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2012; Xie et al., 2009). Additionally, moss crusts can
354 significantly reduce short-wave radiation compared to bare soil, altering the land surface energy
355 balance (Xiao & Bowker, 2020). Second, the crust supports a microbiome rich in heat- and drought-
356 tolerant microorganisms (Meier et al., 2021). These microbes' metabolic activities alter the physical
357 and chemical properties of sandy soils, enhancing their resistance to extreme temperatures and
358 drought. Indeed, our measurements of microbial characteristics in the crust layer and the 0–5 cm
359 soil depth revealed significant differences in microbial community composition, survival strategies,
360 biomass, diversity, and functioning (Fig. S4–S6). Specifically, dominant bacterial phyla differed
361 across layers and subsoil (e.g., *Cyanobacteriota* in the lichen crust, *Pseudomonadota* in the moss
362 crust, and *Bacillota* in the 0-5 cm soil depth). Fungal communities differed as well, with *Ascomycetes*

363 dominating crust layers and *Basidiomycetes* dominating the 0-5 cm soil depth. Microbial biomass
364 and diversity indicators—including microbial biomass nitrogen (MBN), phospholipid fatty acids
365 (PLFAs), fungi, bacteria, and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF)—along with microbial richness,
366 diversity, and network complexity, were higher in crust layers compared to the 0–5 cm soil depth
367 Furthermore, enzyme activities and functional genes related to carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus
368 cycling were significantly elevated in crust layers compared to the subsoil, reflecting the enhanced
369 microbial activity and function in these surface layers. The enrichment of microorganisms in the
370 crust layer significantly boosts the abundance of enzymes and functional genes involved in C, N,
371 and P cycling. This enhances the homeostatic cycling of these elements, making the crust layer more
372 resistant and resilient to the negative effects of global change, but also allowing BSCs to thrive in
373 nutrient-poor soils, arid environments, intense solar radiation, and temperature fluctuations typical
374 of desert ecosystems.

375 While our results indicate that subsoil SMF is negatively affected by temperature and solar
376 radiation, this effect appears to be mitigated by the physical protection provided by the crust, as
377 shown by a less steep slope of the relationship between these climatic variables and SMF under
378 crusts compared to bare soil (Fig. 4). Our findings also suggest that as BSCs develop, the negative
379 influence of climate on subsoil SMF decreases, with the depth of influence shrinking from 0-20cm
380 in cyanobacterial crusts to 0-2 cm in lichen and moss crusts. We propose that the synergistic
381 interplay of the following mechanisms collectively drives this phenomenon: (1) Structural barrier
382 effects: This study found that moss crusts develop thicker (5–10×), rougher surfaces compared to
383 cyanobacterial crusts, reducing kinetic energy of rainfall penetration and thermal conductivity. This
384 physical barrier limits climate impacts (e.g., UV radiation, wind erosion) to the 0–2 cm layer,
385 protecting deeper soils (>5 cm) from physicochemical degradation; (2) Microbial functional
386 redundancy: Moss crusts host diverse microbial communities (e.g., Firmicutes, Basidiomycota) with
387 high functional redundancy. Metabolic mechanisms (e.g., osmolyte synthesis under drought) sustain
388 nutrient cycling even during climatic stress, confining disturbances to the surface layer (Song et al.,
389 2024); (3) Chemical buffering via metabolites: Moss-secreted phenolics (e.g., gallic acid) and LEA
390 proteins accumulate in the 0–2 cm layer, chelating heavy metals and suppressing pathogens. These
391 metabolites also serve as slow-release carbon sources, stabilizing microbial activity under
392 fluctuating climates (Liu et al., 2024); (4) Hydro-Thermal regulation: Moss crusts capture 70–90%

393 of atmospheric moisture (fog/dew), reducing deep infiltration. Simultaneously, their low thermal
394 conductivity buffers diurnal temperature fluctuations, it may have inhibited organic carbon
395 mineralization in deeper layers (Liu et al., 2006). This mechanism demonstrates that BSCs
396 succession, through physical structure optimization and microbial functional enhancement, confines
397 the negative impacts of climatic stress to the surface layer, thereby protecting SMF in deeper soil
398 depth. Our findings highlight that well-developed moss crusts exhibit remarkable capacity to buffer
399 climate change impacts, while simultaneously creating favorable microhabitats for herbaceous plant
400 growth under future climatic challenges such as rising temperatures and prolonged droughts. Our
401 study provides new empirical evidence that, as global change accelerates (Phillips et al., 2022),
402 protecting and fostering BSCs in arid regions will be key to sustaining soil function and ensuring
403 ecosystem resilience.

404 *4.3 BSCs succession moderates the effects of soil and crust properties on crust layer SMF*

405 Compared with the climatic factors that can affect the SMF of BSCs in deeper soil layers, soil
406 and crust properties primarily influenced SMF in the crust layer. However, our results indicate that
407 as BSCs develop, the negative effect of soil pH decreases, while the positive effect of crust thickness
408 significantly increases, indicating that crust development directly and actively regulates the effects
409 of soil and crust properties on the SMF of the crust layer. On the other hand, soil pH, which strongly
410 influences nutrient turnover and microbial activity (Kemmitt et al., 2006; Nie et al., 2017), showed
411 a negative correlation with SMF in cyanobacterial and lichen crusts. The relatively high pH levels
412 in these crust types (i.e. 7.34 and 7.24, respectively) likely reduced the solubility of nutrients such
413 as N and P, hindering plant growth and lowering SMF (Chytry et al., 2007; Tyler, 2003).
414 Interestingly, the relatively lower pH levels in moss crusts (6.95 on average) likely explain why pH
415 did not significantly affect SMF, as mosses can secrete acids that lower soil pH and enhance nutrient
416 availability (Yan et al., 2020). Thus, our results hint a pH threshold of around 7.0 may determine
417 the relationship with SMF, where values above this threshold show a negative correlation, and with
418 mosses likely helping to buffer this negative impact through decreases in soil pH.

419 The physical properties of the BSCs -such as compressive strength (Cs), roughness (Rs) and
420 thickness (Tn)- are important indicators of their development (Wang et al., 2009). Our study
421 provides novel observational insights into how these properties relate directly to SMF. For instance,
422 our results clearly indicate that a higher compressive strength of cyanobacterial and lichen crusts

423 significantly improves SMF. Previous studies have shown that with the proliferation of -especially
424 filamentous- cyanobacteria, a mechanical binding effect coupled with the adhesive properties of
425 their extracellular secretions leads to a tighter, stronger crust, increasing its compressive strength
426 (Adessi et al., 2018). Therefore, the increase in Cs of cyanobacterial crusts likely reflects their
427 developmental progress, explaining the positive relationship between higher Cs and improved SMF.
428 However, in moss crusts, Cs was compressive strength in moss crusts was negatively correlated
429 with SMF, likely to structural specificities of these crusts. Thus, cyanobacteria and lichen form a
430 thin crusts tightly adhering to the ground, making compressive strength an reliable measure of
431 development and soil functionality. In contrast, mosses form thicker crusts with noticeable height,
432 making crust thickness a better indicator of development than compressive strength or roughness.
433 Indeed, our results clearly show that greater moss crust thickness is positively linked to enhanced
434 SMF in the crust layer. Further, structural equation models show that lichen crust properties enhance
435 SMF mainly in the crust layers, but moss crust properties also affect deeper layers (0-5 cm) beneath
436 the crust. These results underscore the role of moss development in improving deeper soil function
437 and highlights the importance of protecting mosses to maintain healthy soils (Eldridge et al., 2023).

438 **5. Conclusion**

439 Our study provides new empirical evidence that nutrient content in the 0-20 cm soil depth and
440 SMF at least in the 0-10 cm depth significantly increase as BSCs progress from cyanobacterial to
441 lichen to moss stages. We demonstrate that while climate is the primary driver of SMF in BSC layers,
442 its influence—and that of soil factors—decreases as BSCs develop, whereas the influence of crust
443 factors increases. Notably, our results show that the effects of climate on SMF is strongly depth-
444 and BSC type-dependent (i.e. differ between the crust layer (positive) and the subsoil (negative),
445 extends to a depth of 20 cm in cyanobacterial crusts but is limited to 0–2 cm below lichen and moss
446 crusts. Altogether, our findings underscore the importance of preserving and promoting BSC
447 development to enhance surface soil fertility and mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on
448 dryland ecosystem multifunctionality. Further, they indicate that assessments of ecosystem
449 stability in arid regions must account for the extensive BSC coverage and consider the varying
450 responses of different BSC types to environmental factors.

451 **Author contributions**

452 All authors contributed intellectual input and assistance to this study and manuscript.

453 **Mingming Wang** and **Boyi song** analyzed the data and wrote the manuscript. **Jorge Durán** and
454 **Xiaobing Zhou** review the manuscript. **Ye Tao, Benfeng Yin, Jing Zhang, Xiaoying Rong,**
455 **Xiaobing Zhou, Yuanming Zhang** desinged the research. **Yonggang Li, Shihang Zhang, Hao**
456 **Guo, Yongxing Lu, Wei Hang, Jungang Yang, Fan Du** contributed to field sampling and
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468 **Data Availability Statement**

469 The soil data and biological soil crusts (BSCs) physical property data used in this paper were
470 measured personally by the experiment. The climate data were sourced from multiple databases.
471 Mean annual temperature (MAT) data were obtained from the MODIS MOD11A Global
472 Temperature Grid (<https://doi.org/10.5067/MODIS/MOD11A1.006>), a MOD11A1 V6 product that
473 provides daily surface temperature (LSTV) and emissivity values in a 1 km grid (Rodell et al., 2004).
474 Aridity (AI) data were extracted from the CGIAR raster (Consortium for Spatial Information; 1x1
475 km resolution) (Hu et al., 2021). Solar radiation (Srad) was obtained from the Terra Climate dataset
476 (University of Idaho; <https://doi:10.1038/sdata.2017.191>; Yan et al., 2020).

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478

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747 **Fig. Legends**

748 **Fig. 1** Soil sampling site distribution: (a) illustrates the spatial arrangement of sampling plots and
749 locations of sampling points within the study area. Figure based on the standard map GS(2020)4619
750 of the Map Service System (<http://bzdt.ch.mnr.gov.cn/>); Ministry of Natural Resources of the
751 People's Republic of China. The boundary of the standard map has not been modified.
752 Representative images of sample types: (b). Bare sand; (c). Cyanobacterial crust; (d). Lichen crust;
753 (e). Moss crust.

754 **Fig. 2** Soil organic carbon (SOC), total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP), ammonium nitrogen
755 ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$), nitrate nitrogen ($\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$), and available phosphorus (AP) at different soil depths and
756 crust types. Different uppercase letters indicate nutrient differences among crusts at the same soil
757 depth. Different lowercase letters indicate differences among soil depths within same crust. S (Sand),
758 C (Cyanobacterial crust), L(Lichen crust), M (Moss crust).

759 **Fig. 3** Soil multifunctionality (SMF) at different soil depths for various crust types. Different
760 uppercase letters indicate SMF differences among crust types at the same soil depth, and different
761 lowercase letters indicate SMF differences among soil depths within the same crust.

762 **Fig. 4** Relationships between SMF and climate factors -i.e. mean annual precipitation (MAP), aridity,
763 and solar radiation (Srad)- for sand, cyanobacterial, lichen, and moss crusts. Lines represent fitted
764 linear ordinary least square (OLS) models, with shaded areas indicating 95% of confidence intervals.

765 **Fig. 5** Random Forest mean predictor importance (% of increase of MSE) of environmental drivers
766 (Climate, Crust, and Soil) on SMF. Climate: MAT, Aridity, Srad; Crust: Cs, Rs, Tn; Soil: pH, EC,
767 SWC. Significance level: *, $P \leq 0.05$; **, $P \leq 0.01$; ***, $P \leq 0.001$.

768 **Fig. 6** Structural equation models (SEMs) showing direct and indirect effects of different variables
769 on SMF. Climate, crust, and soil variables were grouped into compound variables. The number next
770 to each measured variable represents its coefficient with SMF. Red and blue lines indicate positive
771 and negative relationships, respectively, and the direction of the arrow shows the causal relationship
772 between the two variables. The arrow width is proportional to the path coefficient, and the numbers
773 next to the arrows are the standardized prediction coefficients for each causal path. The fill color
774 and border together represent the total effect, the border alone represents the direct effect, while the
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